

**THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE DETERMINATION OF AN
OFFENSIVE SITUATION IN A SPECIAL LINGUISTIC EXPERTISE**

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Annotation. This article examines the methodological features of identifying abusive situations in special linguistic expertise. Also, the approaches used in the practice of linguistic expertise are described and a critical analysis of them is given.

Keywords: special linguistic expertise, stroke, Uzbek language, applied linguistics, negative information, expert-linguist, stroke, honor, personal dignity, linguistics, communication, communicative rudeness, linguistics, expertise, communication, speech behavior, speech act, addressee, addressee , speech, social portrait.

In special linguistic expertise, the problem of insult is considered one of the most complex issues. Although insult as a speech act is well distinguished from other forms in certain respects, the problem of evaluation of insult in the special linguistic expertise of the Uzbek language has not yet been fully resolved. In the theory of linguistic expertise, the problem of abuse is not clearly defined, and in the practice of expertise, there is no single basis for making research decisions. Undoubtedly, the legal aspect of the problem of abuse is also related to its existence. Legal and linguistic aspects are often not clearly distinguished in the work of theorists and practitioners of linguistic expertise, and the "legal" aspect is often considered more important than the "linguistic" one. Therefore, the description of insult in legal linguistics is influenced by legal definitions and structures, which makes it difficult to evaluate the original linguistic model of this

phenomenon. The linguistic theories that a particular researcher uses to describe bullying are almost never clearly stated, so these theories have to be separated from the overall context of the specific study. The purpose of this article is to study and analyze the theories of linguists on the conduct of special linguistic expertise in cases of abuse and on the theoretical basis of expert decision-making .

First of all, let's pay attention to the terms linguistic expertise and special linguistic expertise. Linguistic expertise is considered a field of applied linguistics that requires a lot of knowledge, and it represents a qualified opinion on practical issues in a specific field of activity based on available scientific research [1; 751]. At the same time, expert activity is not the same as scientific activity as a process of knowledge of objective reality, but is based on new knowledge obtained as a result of a comprehensive and reliable study of processes or phenomena using the principles and methods of knowledge available in science [2; 28-38].

Special linguistic expertise is an examination of speech activity at the initiative of any interested individual or legal entity.

The authors of the book "Linguistic expertise in Uzbek" described the process of linguistic expertise as follows. Checking oral or written texts, which are the product of specific speech activity, for compliance with language norms, giving recommendations on eliminating spelling and stylistic errors, what kind of meaning the lexical units used in the text express, their compliance with the requirements of the text, to which object specific goals, such as determining the purpose of the speech, revealing the underlying meaning hidden in the text, determining whether the intended meaning is correctly reflected in the text, developing recommendations for editing the text, and conducting analyzes of the legal consequences of the product of speech activity. researches based on the formal and substantive analysis of the text is considered a process of linguistic expertise [3; 4].

"Contradictory oral and written texts can serve as a basis for linguistic examination. Verbal texts, telephone correspondence, audio and video messages,

emergency calls can be public appeals aimed at various racial discrimination, insults, defamation, propaganda" [4; 333-337]. Turning to the topic of insult presented in this opinion . Several methods have been developed to determine the presence of insult in a speech act, let's analyze them.

In linguistics, two approaches are distinguished when considering the phenomenon of abuse: text-centered and lexico-centric. It is recognized that these two approaches represent two different aspects of describing the same subject. The textual approach is represented by options of stylistic analysis and functional-pragmatic analysis. The lexicocentric approach was first developed in the book "The concept of honor and dignity, insult and normativism in the texts of law and media", and now, in our opinion, it is not a holistic approach, but only theoretically developed by Golev and his students. developed.

Sternin, Antonova, Karpov, Shamanova distinguish ten diagnostic signs of abuse:

1. Reporting negative information about a person.
2. Relation of negative information to a specific person.
3. Factual nature of negative information.
4. Mass distribution of information.
5. Disruptive nature of the information (i.e. language referring to violations of certain ethical standards or laws).
6. Informational (not subjective-emotional) purpose of the message.
7. Indecent (i.e. obscene) form of speech.
8. Generalization of the negative description of the addressee.
9. Presence of proven intent to insult.
10. Inaccuracy of negative information reported about a person or organization.

According to the authors, all ten of the listed signs must be present in order to determine the state of abuse.

However, in our opinion, some of the signs highlighted by the above authors are controversial.

It is difficult to relate the offensive speech act to the factual nature of the negative information (item 3 of the list above), because often the opinions studied to check whether there are linguistic signs of insult are not factual, but evaluative in nature. Therefore, in our opinion, it is wrong to include a factual feature in the list of mandatory diagnostic signs of abuse.

The need to determine the public nature of information dissemination during the examination process also raises doubts (item 4 of the above list). In our opinion, solving such issues does not require special knowledge. The investigator or the court itself can determine whether the statements are public by analyzing the situation.

According to the approach proposed by Sternin, Antonova, Karpov and Shamanova in diagnostic sign 9 above, a linguist-expert can identify speech signs of intention in the text and note that they may indicate that the insult was intentional. However, the final conclusion on the existence of intent is made by the court. In our opinion, it is inappropriate and beyond the competence of the expert to identify any signs that the insult was intentional. Because an expert linguist cannot determine the true purpose of the statement. The intentional component includes the person's awareness of the social danger of his actions, foreseeing the possibility or inevitability of socially dangerous consequences and wanting them to happen. In this case, in our opinion, attention should be paid to determining the communicative purpose of the author of the text.

In conclusion, it is necessary to reconsider the diagnostic signs of abuse described above.

In our opinion, the presented classification of lexical and phraseological units, which in certain contexts of use may be offensive to some people, is too broad. Using this classification, it becomes possible to include almost any word that

negatively evaluates a person, his characteristics and behavior as offensive expressions.

Summarizing the above, despite many developments in the field of forensic linguistic expertise in insult cases, there is no uniform methodology. The reason for this situation is the lack of scientific research in the field and the dispersion of the ongoing developments.

It is necessary to develop a unified, generally accepted scientific-methodical approach and system of concepts of special linguistic expertise in cases of insult. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to hold joint roundtables, seminars, conferences and other events with the participation of representatives of expert organizations and scientific schools. These activities will serve to discuss, test and improve already developed methods and recommendations for identifying signs of abuse in texts.

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